

DISCONTINUOUS CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED FROM RECLAIMED WOVEN PREPREG WASTE

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates a potential value-added composites manufacturing route for reclaimed prepreg off-cut waste consisting of woven carbon fibre reinforcement. The proposed approach focuses on reprocessing prepreg off-cuts into chip-based sheet moulding compound (referred to as Chip-SMC) that can be compression moulded like a conventional sheet moulding compound (SMC). The advantage of this approach is that the limited mechanical performance offered by fibres of finite lengths can be enhanced through the application of stiffening geometry such as ribs and bosses. A laboratory-scale experimental method has been developed for manufacturing Chip-SMCs and the flow behaviour of the new materials has been characterised using the in-plane squeeze flow tests under representative compression moulding conditions. Various chip sizes and areal masses have been investigated to understand how these material parameters affect the flow behaviour of the material, where the flow behaviour has been assessed in terms of the compressive stress-strain relationship and the area increase of the charge due to squeeze flow. Preliminary tensile testing has also been performed to compare the mechanical properties of different materials in terms of tensile modulus and strength, and the correlation between the flow behaviour and the mechanical properties will be investigated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites manufacturing using prepreg typically generates 30%-50% of manufacturing waste [1], which usually ends up in landfill, having negative impact on the environment and resulting in substantial costs. Research has shown that the CO₂ emissions associated with manufacturing virgin material is significantly higher (up to 80% [2]) than that for retrieving fibres from manufacturing scrap. Developing commercially viable solutions to reclaim and reuse carbon fibre prepreg is therefore of great industrial interest, increasing material efficiency, reducing manufacturing cost, and most importantly avoiding landfill. The key to prepreg reuse is to handle the manufacturing waste 'here-and-now' to eliminate further cost and emissions during transportation, developing intermediate products that fit readily within existing manufacturing processes and infrastructures. Recycling prepreg composites is difficult since thermosetting resins cannot be depolymerised easily due to the high cross-linking density of the constituents, therefore fibre/matrix separation is difficult without devaluing these materials. In addition, it is difficult to collect, identify, sort, and separate scrap material from end-of-life components, further increasing the complexity and cost of recycling.

Prepreg off-cuts typically contain fibres of a finite length, therefore any potential recycling strategy should focus on improving the processibility of this material to offset the disadvantages of the resulting discontinuous fibres, using intelligent topological design to maximise mechanical performance. Several approaches have been explored for processing discontinuous prepreg, including chip-based sheet moulding compound (Chip-SMC), which flows under heat and pressure to fill the mould cavity when compression moulded. Commercial examples using virgin prepreg include Hexcel's HexMC and DowAksa's Engineered Moulding Compound (EMC). This approach potentially offers the most robust way of reprocessing prepreg scraps, tolerating any size or shape of material off-cuts, utilising 100% of the waste. However, a compounding facility is required to deposit and consolidate the prepreg chips into an intermediate sheet, as it is difficult to handle and process the loose chips directly. Existing prepreg-based SMCs usually consist of fibre lengths similar to conventional SMCs (e.g. 12.5mm, 25mm and

50mm), but the level of in-cavity flow is limited by the higher fibre content (>60% volume fraction compared to <40% volume fraction for conventional SMCs) and the high molecular weight of the resin system. The mechanical properties of Chip-SMCs are expected to be different from conventional SMCs partly due to the difference in flow behaviour, but also due to the difference in the fibre packing arrangement, as the chips will be derived from both unidirectional (UD) and woven prepreg offcuts, rather than tows or UD platelets.

Most Chip-SMCs available in both the commercial and the academic domains have been manufactured from UD prepreg [3, 4], with very few studies on woven prepreg based Chip-SMC [2, 5]. The majority of studies on woven prepreg Chip-SMC did not attempt to explore the material's ability to flow, typically laminating the chips net-shape and compression moulding with little or no flow [2, 5]. The issue with such an approach is that the warp and weft tows remain interlaced together in these woven prepreg based chips, creating discontinuities at the edges of the chips that can lead to high stress concentration and potential weaknesses in the material.

Little effort has therefore been made to investigate ways to engineer the material such that the optimum compromise between the flow behaviour and the mechanical properties can be achieved. The hypothesis made in this paper is that the material and the moulding process should be designed to promote high level of flows to encourage the dispersion of individual fibre tows, to improve the homogeneity of the material and minimise weak links. The design challenge is that the chips should be small enough to promote dispersion of tows, but large enough to retain the fibre length in the composite.

This paper presents experimental studies on the flow behaviour and mechanical properties of woven prepreg Chip-SMC. A laboratory-scale manufacturing route will be developed to reprocess woven prepreg into Chip-SMCs of various chip sizes and areal mass. The flow behaviour of each Chip-SMC will be investigated through in-plane squeeze flow testing under typical SMC compression moulding conditions. Visual inspection will be performed to assess the quality of the specimens and the level of tow dispersion after squeeze flow tests. Quantitative comparison between different materials will be made in terms of the compressive stress-strain response and the increase in specimen area caused by squeeze flow. Flat plaques will be manufactured via compression moulding processes and cut into tensile specimens for tensile properties comparison.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Manufacturing of Chip-SMCs

The woven prepreg used in this study was an epoxy based material supplied by DowAksa, with 12k tow size, 2x2 twill weave and 55% fibre volume fraction. The material is not commercially available, therefore further details of the material will not be disclosed due to reasons of confidentiality. Figure 1 presents images from the manufacturing of Chip-SMCs. The prepreg material was cut into square chips using a Zund CNC fabric cutting table (Figure 1a). All chips were cut at 0/90° in relation to the direction of the fibres, and three different square chip sizes were studied, with edge lengths of 12.5mm, 17.2mm, and 25mm.

Lamination of loose prepreg chips was carried out by shuffling the chips within a sealed square plastic envelope until the distribution of the chips was visually uniform. The chips were laminated into three nominal areal masses: 3000gsm, 6000gsm and 8000gsm. While conventional SMCs have typical nominal areal mass of 2000gsm, this is usually because higher areal mass will increase the difficulty to fully infuse the resin into the dry fibre network during the compaction process. The fibres in prepreg on the other hand are already impregnated thoroughly, and increasing the areal mass of the Chip-SMC can effectively reduce the layup time when preparing the initial charge for compression moulding. The areal mass of the chips was determined from the area of the envelope and the nominal mass of the Chip-SMC inside. Envelopes containing the chips were then positioned onto the conveyor belt of a Schmidt & Heinzmann compounding line (see Figure 1c), and compacted at 3 bar and 50°C (see Figure 1d). The Chip-SMCs (see Figure 1b) were then removed from the envelopes before the flow characterization studies or compression moulding.

Figure 1: Manufacturing of Chip-SMCs. (a) 25mm loose chips. (b) 25mm, 3000gsm Chip-SMC. (c) sealed envelopes containing chips before entering the compaction chamber. (d) sealed envelopes containing chips after exiting the compaction chamber.

2.2 Flow characterisation

Flow characterisation for Chip-SMCs was performed using in-plane squeeze flow testing. A squeeze flow rig shown in Figure 2 installed on a 250kN Zwick servo-hydraulic testing machine was employed. The squeeze flow rig consisted of a pair of 350mm × 350mm testing plates heated by cartridge heaters. The testing plates were attached to a die set with four guide columns to ensure parallelism of the testing plates. An extensometer was attached to the side of the testing plates for accurately measuring the displacement of the moving plate. Circular-shaped squeeze flow testing specimens with a diameter of 100 mm (Figure 3a) were stamped out from the Chip-SMCs using a clicker-press. All tests were performed at a mould temperature of 100°C, which was lower than the recommended moulding temperature of 150°C in order to slow down the curing reaction of the material and provide the operator sufficient time to load the specimen and start the test. All tests were performed at a constant speed of 1 mm/s with a 200 kN force limit. After the end of the test, specimens were held between the plates at a constant cavity height for 20 minutes to allow a sufficient degree of cure before the specimen was removed from the rig (see Figure 3b).

The flow behaviour of each specimen was assessed in terms of the compressive stress-strain response and the area increase of the specimen after the squeeze flow testing. Detailed methods for determining the stress-strain response and the area increase of the specimen can be found in [6]. VORAFUSE® EMC, supplied by DowAksa, was selected as a commercial SMC to provide a benchmark for the flow behaviour of the Chip-SMCs. The baseline SMC was derived from a UD prepreg consisting of the same epoxy resin system as the Chip-SMC, with fibre length ranges from 27mm – 54mm, 1048gsm areal mass and 55% fibre volume fraction.

Figure 2: The squeeze flow rig employed for flow characterisation.

Figure 3: An 12.5 mm, 3000 gsm Chip-SMC specimen (a) before and (b) after the squeeze flow test.

2.3 Compression moulding and tensile testing

Four flat plaques of 550mm x 550mm x 2.5mm were manufactured using the 17.5mm Chip-SMC to investigate the material's processing behaviour during actual compression moulding processes, as well as to perform a preliminary study for the tensile properties of the material. Two of the plaques were moulded using a square charge with an initial coverage of 100% while the other two were moulded using a square charge with an initial coverage of 80% (see Figure 4), and all charges were single-ply. This resulted in a charge areal mass of 3800gsm for the 100% initial coverage and 4750gsm for the 80% initial coverage. Experimental compression moulding was performed on an Engel V-Duo 1700 tonne press. The mould temperatures were 165°C at the bottom (female mould half) and 160°C at the top (male mould half). The compression moulding process was initially under the speed control with 1mm/s

closing speed and changed to force control at a switch-over force of 500kN. The holding force was 3500kN.

Figure 4: Charge layout of 17.5mm Chip-SMC with 80% initial coverage.

Tensile specimens were cut at 0° and 90° from each plaque to examine the directionality and homogeneity of the material. Straight-sided specimens of 250mm long and 25mm wide were tested on a Zwick 250kN universal testing machine according to ASTM D3039 and 5 repeats were tested for each specimen configuration. An extension rate of 1 mm/min was used in conjunction with a sampling rate of 1 Hz. The exact thickness and width values for stress calculations were determined by averaging values measured at five positions along the gauge length. Average tensile strain was measured using a clip-on extensometer with a 50 mm gauge length. The same baseline SMC for benchmarking the flow behaviour was also used for benchmarking the tensile properties, but the baseline SMC plaques were moulded using a 60% initial coverage according to the material supplier's recommendation.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Flow characterisation

Table 1 summarises the specimen mass information and the results from the specimen area analysis. Figure 5 presents the area increase data after testing for each chip size and nominal areal mass, where the dotted red line indicates the area increase of the baseline SMC specimen. Area increase is a good indicator for the material's ability to flow, which is typically dominated by two deformation mechanisms for SMC: compaction and spreading of tows and dispersion of tows. The area increase measures the level of tow dispersion. However, it should be noted that area increase alone cannot be directly compared between specimens of different masses, because specimen with larger mass contains more tows, which naturally leads to higher level of dispersion. According to Figure 5 for the same nominal areal mass, specimens with smaller chips generally experience a larger increase in area after testing. The 3000gsm specimens with chip sizes of 12.5mm and 17.5mm both had similar area increase to the baseline SMC (around 200%). However, as the area increase generally decreases with reduced specimen mass, it is expected that these Chip-SMCs would experience lower area increase at an areal mass similar to that of the baseline SMC (1048gsm). This can be explained by the mesoscale fibre architecture: the interlacing tows in Chip-SMCs prohibit the movement of tows, leading to lower levels of fibre dispersion. It is also interesting to note that the 17.5mm chip size had a 50% higher area increase compared to the 25mm chip size, while, the 12.5mm chip size had only 20% higher area increase than the 17.5mm chip size.

This implies a threshold for a critical chip size exists, below which the material’s ability to flow will not be improved any further. This will be investigated in future work using tests on a wider range of chip sizes, considering different chip aspect ratios.

Table 1: Squeeze flow specimen information with the specimen mass and area analysis results.

Chip size [mm]	Nominal areal mass [g/m ²]	Specimen mass [g]	Actual areal mass [g/m ²]	Areal mass difference	Area before test [mm ²]	Area after test [mm ²]		
12.5	3000	20	2,651	- 11.6%	7,543	22,789		
17.5		24	3,181	+ 6.0%		21,409		
25.0		23	3,049	+ 1.6%		19,056		
12.5	6000	42	5,568	- 7.2%		7,543	34,048	
17.5		43	5,700	- 5.0%			32,458	
25.0		47	6,230	+ 3.8%			28,376	
12.5	8000	67	8,882	+ 11.0%			7,543	37,175
17.5		60	7,954	- 0.6%				37,219
25.0		61	8,087	+ 1.1%				32,437

Figure 5: Comparison of specimen area increase after squeeze flow testing for Chip-SMCs of different chip sizes and nominal areal mass and the baseline SMC.

Figure 6 provides a more detailed examination of the Chip-SMC specimens after squeeze flow testing by comparing the surface appearance of two 3000gsm specimens with chip sizes of 12.5 mm and 25 mm. A more even dispersion of fibre tows can be observed for the specimen consisting of 12.5mm chips (Figure 6a) whereas some interlaced fibre tows with the noticeable weave pattern can be seen on the surface of the specimens with 25mm chips (Figure 6b). In addition, convex-shaped bumps can be observed on the sample surface, especially for the 25mm chip size (see images taken at a tilted angle in Figure 6). As shown in the close-up views, these bumps mostly occurred in areas where interlacing fibre

tows existed. The movement of the interlaced tows was restricted within the charge flow, creating regions of high local fibre volume fraction with minimal resin content (i.e. a dry spot). Although such defects might be eliminated in an actual compression moulding process because of the very high pressure built up within a closed mould, the interlacing tows could still lead to possible reduction in the mechanical properties of the material, which will be studied in the next section.

Figure 6: Surface of two specimens with the same areal mass and different chip sizes: (a) 12.5 mm, 3000gsm (more uniform tow dispersion with fewer interlacing tows) and (b) 25 mm, 3000gsm (less uniform tow dispersion with more interlacing tows)

Figure 7 shows the compressive stress-strain relationship obtained from the squeeze flow test for all Chip-SMC specimens. The dotted red curve is the stress-strain result for the baseline SMC. The influence of the areal mass can be observed clearly, as specimens with higher areal mass exhibited lower resistant to compressive pressures during testing. This was possibly because the unstructured layout of chips led to lofting between chips, which effectively became voids in the material. Higher areal mass means there was higher percentage of voids per specimen area, making it easier to compact the specimen. Interestingly, the effect of chip size was less significant in terms of the material's stress-strain response, as indicated by the three distinct groups of curves, which are grouped according to the areal mass. In addition, the curve for the baseline SMC sits closely between the curves for 3000 gsm Chip-SMC with 12.5 mm and 17.5 mm chips, where the three materials also had similar area increase as discussed above. A detailed study on the compressibility of Chip-SMC will be conducted and the results will be compared with the baseline SMC in the future to provide a better overview of the through-thickness constitutive relations.

Figure 7: Comparison of compressive stress-strain response obtained from squeeze flow testing for Chip-SMCs of different chips sizes and nominal areal mass and the baseline SMC.

3.2 Compression moulding and tensile testing

All the plaques were fully filled with no noticeable defects observed from the surface. However, a considerable amount of tows remained in the original interlaced chip format, as expected, based on the flow characterisation results. These can be visually observed from the surface of the plaques (Figure 8). The feasibility of moulding plaques with lower initial charge coverage will be investigated in the future, in order to promote more uniform tow dispersion.

Figure 8: A compression moulded 17.5mm Chip-SMC plaque with 80% initial coverage (4750gsm initial areal mass). Weaves with remaining interlaced tows can be visually seen from the surface of the place as highlighted in the red box.

Figure 9 and Figure 10 compare the tensile modulus and tensile strength between 17.5mm Chip SMC specimens of different initial coverage and specimen orientation against the baseline SMC. Note that the baseline SMC in Figure 9 and Figure 10 was moulded using a 60% initial coverage with the tensile modulus and strength were both averaged between 0 and 90 specimens. According to Figure 9, all Chip-SMC specimens have very similar tensile modulus, which suggests that there is little directionality in the material. The 100% initial coverage specimens tend to experience higher levels of variability (up to 21.7%), which is typical for discontinuous fibre based composites [7]. The tensile modulus of the Chip-SMC is up to 34.3% lower than that for the baseline SMC, which could be possibly due to the shorter fibre lengths in this material (17.5mm for the Chip-SMC and a mixed fibre length between 27mm and 54mm for the baseline SMC). The difference in tensile modulus is also likely to be due to higher voids content in the Chip-SMC caused by the reduced flow.

The tensile strength results presented in Figure 10 also shows little directionality in the material, such that the tensile strength values were similar between 0° and 90° for both initial coverages. However, the 80% coverage specimens have shown 20% increase in tensile strength compared to the 100% coverage specimens, which has demonstrated the benefit of increasing the level of flow. When compared to the tensile strength of the baseline SMC, the Chip-SMC exhibits an average tensile strength that is 64.6% lower than that of the baseline SMC. This is not only caused by the shorter fibre length and the potential higher voids content due to the less flow, but also the meso-scale architecture in the Chip-SMC specimens (Figure 8), where the interlaced tows can create stress concentrations in the material. It should be noted that unlike the Chip-SMC, the mechanical properties of the baseline SMC would be less affected by the initial coverage because initial fibre dispersion is already uniform. The Chip-SMCs on the other hand relies on high levels of flow to break up the interlacing tows and reduce the critical stress concentrations in the material [7].

Figure 9: Tensile modulus comparison between 17.5mm Chip-SMC and the baseline SMC specimens, for different initial coverage and specimen orientations. The baseline SMC was moulded using a 60% initial coverage and the tensile modulus value was averaged between 0° and 90° specimens.

Figure 10: Tensile strength comparison between 17.5mm Chip-SMC and the baseline SMC specimens of different initial coverage and specimen orientation. The baseline SMC was moulded using a 60% initial coverage and the tensile strength value was averaged between 0° and 90° specimens.

Figure 11 presents examples of different types of Chip-SMC specimens after tensile testing. In general, final fracture can occur at any location along the gauge length. It is interesting to note that for the 100% coverage specimens, the majority of the specimens failed with one single, relatively straight crack over the width of the specimen, while for the 80% coverage specimens, most specimens had multiple fracture sites, with catastrophic fracture occurring with more complicated crack geometry. It is not clear at this stage what has caused this difference in failure mode between the two specimen types. Microscopic analysis and full-field strain mapping using Digital Image Correction (DIC) will be utilised in future testing to study the correlation between the mesoscale fibre architecture and the failure mode of the material.

Figure 11: Examples of different types of 17.5mm Chip-SMC specimen after tensile testing.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A laboratory-scale method for reprocessing woven prepreg into Chip-SMCs has been developed. Chip-SMCs consisting of chip sizes of 12.5mm, 17.5mm and 25mm with nominal areal masses of 3000gsm, 6000gsm and 8000gsm have been manufactured. All Chip-SMCs have been characterised using squeeze flow testing and benchmarked against a baseline commercial SMC. The squeeze flow results have shown that materials with smaller chip sizes experience more area increase during squeeze flow, but the Chip-SMCs general experience less area increase compared to the baseline SMC as the interlacing tow prohibit the fibre dispersion. Higher number of interlacing tows have been observed in specimens consisting of larger chip sizes after squeeze flow testing, which have resulted in surface bumps in the specimen. Analysis of the compressive stress-strain relationship has suggested that the material's resistance to compression stresses decreases with increasing areal mass, but chip size has little influence on the compressive stress-strain response.

Flat plaques have been compression moulded using the 17.5mm Chip-SMC with 80% and 100% initial coverage. All plaques were fully filled with no visible surface defects. Tensile testing of the plaques has suggested that there is no directionality in the plaques, and the fibre volume fraction is uniform. The Chip-SMC specimens had 34.3% lower tensile modulus compared to the baseline, possibly due to the shorter fibre length and smaller initial charge size. The tensile strength of the Chip-SMC has shown a greater reduction (64.6%) compared to the baseline SMC, which is not only due to the short fibre length, but also because of the stress concentrations caused by the interlaced woven tow architecture.

Future work will explore a wider range of chip sizes and also different chip aspect ratios, using DIC and microscopy to understand the failure modes of these Chip-SMC materials.

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